

Masers in Astrophysical Plasmas (MAPs): unveiling the coherent emission of Pulsars, Magnetars and their connection with Fast Radio Bursts

Version 1

Description

Observations in astrophysics reveal that coherent radiation emerges from hot relativistic plasmas immersed in the intense fields surrounding compact objects. Despite various proposed explanations, the mechanisms driving such coherent processes remain unknown. A particularly promising avenue is the electron cyclotron instability (ECMI). Our recent results on extreme plasma physics in strong magnetic fields, incorporating Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) effects, demonstrated that the ECMI can operate without the previously assumed finely-tuned conditions, facilitating the maser mechanism under a wide variety of astrophysical scenarios. To connect our discovery with the physics of compact objects, such as understanding the origins of Fast Radio Bursts and pulsar emission, we aim to utilize cutting-edge Particle-in-Cell (PIC) simulations with the massively parallel OSIRIS simulation code. PIC simulations provide a foundational approach, allowing us to investigate these processes from first principles but are very computationally demanding. The utilization of large-scale High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems is crucial for detailed large-scale simulations. This allows us to integrate realistic magnetic field configurations that faithfully replicate the conditions surrounding pulsars and magnetars. This approach bridges the gap between theoretical models and the processes governing coherent emission in compact objects like pulsars and magnetars, which are a confirmed source of Fast Radio Bursts. Advancing our fundamental understanding will not only illuminate astrophysical observations but also inform the design of laboratory experiments that can study these fundamental plasma processes in this novel regime.

Funder

Fundação para a Ciência e a
Tecnologia, I.P. | FCT

Grant

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Researchers

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Organizations

GoLP/Instituto de Plasmas e Fusão Nuclear, Instituto Superior
Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, 1049-001 Lisbon, Portugal

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Masers in Astrophysical Plasmas \(MAPs\): unveiling the coherent emission of Pulsars, Magnetars and their connection with Fast Radio Bursts](#)

Description:

Observations in astrophysics reveal that coherent radiation emerges from hot relativistic plasmas immersed in the intense fields surrounding compact objects. Despite various proposed explanations, the mechanisms driving such coherent processes remain unknown. A particularly promising avenue is the electron cyclotron instability (ECMI). Our recent results on extreme plasma physics in strong magnetic fields, incorporating Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) effects, demonstrated that the ECMI can operate without the previously assumed finely-tuned conditions, facilitating the maser mechanism under a wide variety of astrophysical scenarios. To connect our discovery with the physics of compact objects, such as understanding the origins of Fast Radio Bursts and pulsar emission, we aim to utilize cutting-edge Particle-in-Cell (PIC) simulations with the massively parallel OSIRIS simulation code. PIC simulations provide a foundational approach, allowing us to investigate these processes from first principles but are very computationally demanding. The utilization of large-scale High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems is crucial for detailed large-scale simulations. This allows us to integrate realistic magnetic field configurations that faithfully replicate the conditions surrounding pulsars and magnetars. This approach bridges the gap between theoretical models and the processes governing coherent emission in compact objects like pulsars and magnetars, which are a confirmed source of Fast Radio Bursts. Advancing our fundamental understanding will not only illuminate astrophysical observations but also inform the design of laboratory experiments that can study these fundamental plasma processes in this novel regime.

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. | FCT

Grants: 2024.11062.CPCA.A3

Project: Masers in Astrophysical Plasmas (MAPs): unveiling the coherent emission of Pulsars, Magnetars and their connection with Fast Radio Bursts

3. License

License: AFL-3.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

FCT - Template in English

Template: FCT - Template in English

Type: Dataset

1 DATA INFORMATION

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

No

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

Numerical

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1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

HDF5

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

>1000 GB

2 DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

Simulation parameters and how to access and read the data

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

No

3 STORAGE AND SECURITY OF DATA AND METADATA

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

Yes

3.1.4 Please describe the type of backup.

Differential backup

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3.1.5 Please describe the frequency of backup.

Monthly

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Not applicable (no sensitive data)

4 PERSONAL DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS AND OWNERSHIP

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

No

4.1.3 How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

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The group reserves the right to manage data prior to publication. Afterwards the data will be made publicly available.

5 DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5.1 Long-term data preservation

5.1.1 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?

All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least 10 years

5.2 Data available for re-use

5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

All data resulting from the project will be made available

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available as soon as article is published

Zenodo

5.2.4 In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use, and under which license?

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

<https://zenodo.org/communities/golp/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

5.2.5 Please confirm if:

The repository is certified

5.2.6 Please indicate whether a persistent identifier will be pursued.

Yes

DOI

5.2.7 Under which license will the data be archived and made available for re-use?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

5.2.8 Describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project.

All software is public or open source

6 RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6.1 Responsibilities and resources for data management

6.1.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?

PABLO JAIME (0000-0003-3085-8406)

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GoLP/IPFN

Management and curating

6.1.2 What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?

The necessary resources for data management and ensuring FAIR principles will be covered through the dedicated time and effort of the Principal Investigator (PI), with no additional funding requested. Data curation, organization, and metadata preparation will be carried out using existing institutional infrastructure and best practices adopted by the research group. No extra budget is required for storage or repository fees, as data will be deposited in publicly available platforms such as Zenodo or institutional repositories that do not charge deposit fees. Data formatting, documentation, and compliance with FAIR principles will be handled by the PI as part of project supervision and reporting duties. Given the PI's experience with open data practices and previous successful deposits of simulation datasets, this approach is considered both feasible and sustainable within the project's existing scope. No additional costs are foreseen in the FCT grant application for this purpose.

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